

IMPACT OF COVID-19 PANDEMIC MITIGATION MEASURES ON STUDENTS SOCIAL COMPETENCE: SURVEY BASED APPROACH.

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Abstract.

Objectives: To inspect the Social Competence level against Covid-19 mitigations measures taken in this pandemic period among University Students.

Design: A survey based approach through electronic and face-to-face survey for students' come up during the pandemic and the relative challenges. In addition, the analysis of quantitative data, from responses related were extracted and interpreted using a manual for social competence.

Setting: The study used a non-probability sampling method based a non-random criteria with convenience samples.

Participants: 114 University students responded to the questionnaires.

Results: The research focused on the Level of Social Competence between two groups of students i.e. students who tested positive and Negative for the Coronavirus. About 114 university students participated, out of which 11 tested Positive and 103 tested negatives.

P-value of 0.00 and Standard Deviation of 19. Stratified regression of (-0.08) revealed a strong negative correlation between the group tested positive and negative. Results showed that level of social competence of students from group that tested positive was described as high whereas an increased level of social competence was seen as very high among students who tested Negative.

Conclusions: Overall, the results accentuate the benefits of communicate field of high learning system and the student aspects of learning environment affected by the pandemic for the sake of improve, keeping on the students' social competence and, support universities teaching methodology.

Keywords: Covid-19 Pandemic, social competence, mitigation measures, e-learning.

Introduction.

In various community, mitigations strategies have been taken to prevent and protect against the rapid proliferation of new coronavirus named Covid-19. Some of them

are total or partial lockdown, the social distancing of two meters among individuals, wearing a facemask, stopping hands shaking, hands sanitizer or water in public places, and stopping all physical classes shifted online by most of schools and colleges. Considering all those strategies, the stigma among students' fear of being contaminated by their colleagues rose after the reopening of physical classes as the pandemic is under control. Those prevention measures habit, have an impact on the social competence of students as they reduced their relationships, flexibility to move back reactivity, especially the capacity to evoke favorable responses from others, empathy, communication skills, a good sense of humour, and a caring attitude. (Bernard, 2008). Moreover, those are key roles for teaching and learning for students.

By looking short identification Coronaviruses, are viruses that can harm both animals and humans' respiratory systems. Coronavirinae is a subfamily of the Coronaviridae family. It has different types commonly known as 229E (alpha coronavirus), NL63 (alpha coronavirus), OC43 (beta coronavirus), HKU1 (beta coronavirus) MERS-CoV, which causes Middle East respiratory syndrome (MERS), and SARS-CoV, It is responsible for severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS), are only

a few of the uncommon variants (SARS). SARS-CoV-2, which causes Coronavirus sickness in 2019, is the most recent strain known as (COVID-19). (Narayana, 2020).

COVID-19 is disseminate mostly when an infected individual coughs, sneezes, or speaks, respiratory droplets are created. The spread of illness extend at the moment that droplets fall on the eyes, nose, or mouth of a person in close contact. Touching the face with contaminated hands can also cause transmission. Because respiratory droplets do not linger in the air for long periods, keeping a distance of six feet from an infected individual may be deemed safe. Coronaviruses can infect metal, glass, or plastic surfaces for several days. Contact with contaminated objects and subsequent touch transmission to the face could be a major method of infection. (WHO, 2020).

Viruses that drift through the air, as opposed to droplet infection, are the hallmark of airborne transmission. It's uncertain whether COVID-19 infection causes airborne transmission. The risk of airborne transmission necessitates the use of additional precautions, such as wearing face masks in public. The incubation period is the same for all humans. The interval between manifestation to COVID-19 and the onset of

symptoms is usually five to six days, although it can be anywhere from one to fourteen days. (WHO, 2020). COVID-19 shows varied impacts on different people. The majority of infected persons will have mild to moderate symptoms and will recover without needing to go to the hospital. (WHO, 2020).

Over 180 nations have been afflicted by the COVID-19 pandemic, which infected around six and a half million humans and put an end to over 383,000 persons. The epidemic stretched medical services, the education system disturbed, and wreaked havoc against economies and businesses, resulting in job instability, deprivation, and disturbed socializing, with solitary, time limit, with other strategies aimed at suppressing the propagation of covid-19 being enacted worldwide. All those decisions were taken as part of the implementation for sustainable development of the 2030 Agenda, which places a high value on the public sector and its employees (UN-DESA, United Nations, 2020).

Unavailability or insufficient of real information and scientific treatment about covid-19 in the early stages of its transmission, allowed it to infiltrate communities before government officials

grasped its gravity. Medical professional, as well as laboratories physicians, and other partners in health professionals consisted among the primary identified as contagion, spreading the expression that a new and extremely infectious pathogen was on the rise. More information about the disease became available, health care professionals, news media officials, and institutions of researchers began to provide mitigation measures to the public and local leaders, which is appropriate in the control of covid-19 transmission. With almost 1.4 billion schools permanently closed, innovative technology-based techniques are being employed to keep the learning process going. This encouraging trend stemming from the recent technological revolution promotes education's resistance to shocks, which is an important aspect of human growth. So, after all of these attempts, what is the effective out-of-school rate? Adjusting the percentage of primary school pupils suffering school closures to account for households with Internet access—and the option to continue organized learning—helps to throw some light on these challenges (UNDP Human-Development-Report-Office, 2020).

To put it another way, it's an optimistic assessment of students' social abilities to stay in school. It's also an overestimate of

inequities between countries because it assumes that putting these systems in place is equally difficult in all circumstances, whether high or low income, with or without broadband, and with or without suitable hardware. Even under optimistic assumptions, the effective out-of-school rate has increased significantly (UNDP, 2020).

Relationships play a role in social rivalry. It entails responsiveness, particularly the capability to evoke others' positive responses; flexibility, including the ability to switch dominant and primary cultures like cross-cultural competence, empathy, communication skills, care, with a sense of humour (Benard, 2008). Social awareness Effectiveness or competence in interpersonal relationships and social circumstances is becoming increasingly crucial in mental health. Social competence entails the capacity to assess social circumstances and identify what is expected or necessary; recognize others' feelings and intentions; and choose the most suitable social behaviors for the scenario. It's worth noting, though, that what's necessary and appropriate for efficient social functioning may likely differ depending on the situation (APA, 2022).

Abilities and behaviors that children require for effective social adaptation are referred to

as social competence. The social competency of a student is determined by a variety of elements, including social skills, social awareness, and self-confidence. The phrase "social skills" refers to a student's understanding of and ability to employ a variety of social actions that are acceptable for each interpersonal learning environment and appealing to others. A student's ability to control egocentric, impulsive, or unfavorable social conduct is also a reflection of their social abilities. The capacity to comprehend colleagues' emotions, recognize subtle social indicators, "read" complicated social situations, and display insight into others' motivations and goals for students is referred to as emotional intelligence. "Student social competency" refers to a student's ability to function in social situations. It describes a student's capacity to form and sustain high quality, mutually gratifying connections while avoiding negative or victimizing treatment from others. Social skills and emotional intelligence can be influenced by variables such as a student's self-confidence or social anxiety. The social milieu, as well as the degree to which the student's skills, interests, and talents match those of peers, can have an impact on social competence. By giving an example, in chemistry, a quiet and studious student may look socially inept in a

peer group full of rowdy, but if a more complimentary peer group can be discovered for him, such as students who share his interests in quiet social media or computers, he may perform great socially.

Peer relationships are very crucial for students in school during adolescence. Peers serve as a social stepping stone for teenagers as they transition away from their emotional dependency on their parents and toward autonomous adult functioning. When children have major problems with their peers, their ability to develop social skills may be at risk of evolution. Students may experience tremendous stress because of peer rejection or victimization, adding to feelings of loneliness and low self-esteem. Moreover, Peer rejection can lead to a downward spiral in one's development. When student with low social skills is rejected, they are frequently excluded from positive peer contacts, which are crucial for social skill development. Accepted students often have more possibilities for playmates and buddies than rejected students do. A teacher may be able to form cooperative learning groups to assist isolated students in making friends in the classroom. Parents may sometimes assist by bringing possible friends over to play or by enrolling their kid in a fulfilling social activity outside of school, such as a religious

organization, sports team, or scouting club. It is critical to offer children favorable possibilities for friendship development since this provides them with an appropriate and pleasant learning environment in which to build social competence.

In a recent study conducted in China, 112, 196, and 68 solitary children and adolescents, aged 6 to 15 years were found to have depression, anxiety, or both (Chen F., 2020). Another study discovered that the COVID-19 outbreak has caused severe psychological discomfort in children and adolescents in India. Comparing to non-isolated youth, individuals have felt vulnerable (66.11 percent), with concerned (68.59 percent), and dreadful (68.59 percent) related to (61.98 percent) (Saurabh K., 2020). Moreover, young peoples between three to eighteen years old in China showed signs relate to irritability, clinging, inattention and concern (Jiao W.Y., 2020).

The aim of this study is to inspect the effect of Covid-19 pandemic mitigations strategies on the university students' social competence, and predicts possible alternative solutions promoting social competence in the teaching and learning environment for university students.

Present Study.

This was an exploratory study to evaluate the level of social competence among university students due to the covid-19 mitigation strategies experienced during this pandemic period as governments used different strategies to prevent and cope with the pandemic. Generally, mitigations taken were the same across the world but the students who tested positive were treated very differently with strong isolation compared to the students who tested negative. The aim of this work was to develop how Covid-19 mitigation measures are applied in different educational institutions. To identify factors that affect student social competence from Covid-19 mitigations strategies. In addition, to evaluate and improve students' social competence in the teaching and learning environment during this pandemic period. There is a significant effect of covid-19 pandemic mitigation measures in regard to students' social competence?

Method.

Participants.

One hundred and fourteen participants were students from different Universities and high learning institutes who experienced online classes taken via two modes of stratified

random sampling. The questionnaire was sent via an online google link and a face-to-face survey by the primary data collection. All of them agreed voluntarily to respond to the questionnaire and to be used for education purposes. Among these participants, 53 were female and 61 were male. Twenty-one participants are Postgraduate students and ninety-three are from the Undergraduate program.

Procedure.

A survey was employed to collect data for this study, as it is the most extensively utilized data-gathering method. It is especially powerful when respondents' responses to questions are used to assess variables. For this study, a self-administered questionnaire was regarded as more convenient than a face-to-face survey, and a google form was sent to the respondents online by social media channels like WhatsApp, Instagram, and email. There are both questionnaires semi-structured and structured, as well as closed-ended and open-ended questions. An individual response took approximately 10 to 15 minutes. Evaluating the social competence of students, survey questionnaire was applied as the basic data collection tool for this research. The manual for social competence scale as a used tool in

this study is designed for 16 plus years of age in school and college students to measure social competence in its three dimensions (personal adequacy, interpersonal adequacy, and communication skills). The scoring pattern for social competence scale answered in the format of four point Likert scale where: (Always = 4, Mostly = 3, Sometimes = 2, Never = 1 in positive nature of Item) and (Always = 1, Mostly = 2, Sometimes = 3, Never = 4 in Negative nature of Item).

Categories	Description	Range of scores
A	Very good	168 - 188
B	Good	148 - 167
C	Average	108 - 147
D	Poor	78 - 107
E	Very poor	47 - 77

Table 1: Level of social competence in terms of total scores. (Latika, Punita. 2013).

Results.

Data screening.

Statistical calculation done for students experienced both negative and positive results of covid-19 tests. However, normal distribution of data was not observed.

Main results.

According to responses received, 114(100%) participants were students of high learning. That means university, colleges and high institutions where 103(90%) are students tested negative and 11(10%) are students tested positive.

Pie chart: distribution according students covid-19 test results.

Participant's scores.

Scores from participants calculated and evaluated using of manual scale for social competence. Moreover, descriptive statistics described accordingly. The histogram of data collected shows clearly the mean of 180.47, median of 178 and standard deviation of 19.63 with maximum score of 230 and 145 minimum for students tested negative. Moreover, mean of 159.73, median is 159,

standard deviation 10.19 with minimum of 141 and maximum is 181 for students experienced positive test.

Tested negative		Tested positive	
Mean	180.47	Mean	159.73
Standard Error	1.93	Standard Error	3.07
Median	178.00	Median	159.00
Mode	172.00	Mode	159.00
Standard Deviation	19.63	Standard Deviation	10.19
Sample Variance	385.33	Sample Variance	103.82
Kurtosis	-0.62	Kurtosis	1.84
Skewness	0.44	Skewness	0.52
Range	85.00	Range	40.00
Minimum	145.00	Minimum	141.00
Maximum	230.00	Maximum	181.00
Sum	18588.00	Sum	1757.00
Count	103.00	Count	11.00

Table 2: Descriptive statistics of data from participants.

According the output table, there was positive significant difference in the positive and negatives groups of students responded as (M=180.46; SD=19) for negative group and (M= 159.7; SD= 10) for positive group. The P = 0.00. Independent samples t-test calculated to compare the total scores from students who had tested positive with others who was tested negative. Results shows the significant difference from students experienced positive test of Covid-19 in score sheet compare to those student with negative test. According to manual scale for social competence.

	<i>Tested negative</i>	<i>Tested positive</i>
Mean	180.47	159.73
Variance	385.33	103.82
Observations	103.00	11.00
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0.00	
df	19.00	
t Stat	5.71	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.00	
t Critical one-tail	1.73	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.00	
t Critical two-tail	2.09	

Table 3: t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances.

Correlation level conducted to test whether mitigation measures taken for both groups of students tested negative or positive, the significant linear relationship between studied groups. Results shows that correlation coefficient value = -0.08 mean total negative linear correlation. Results revealed that there were a strong total negative correlation between students tested negative and positive for other side.

Correlation.		
	<i>Tested negative</i>	<i>Tested positive</i>
Tested negative	1	
Tested positive	-0.08	1

Table 4: Correlation table for both group tested.

Discussion.

The preliminary data analysis revealed a sample with a non-normal distribution. This might indicate that the data is likely to follow a non-normal distribution in its native state. This natural trend is related to the dynamic situational aspects of pandemic emergencies, in which individuals' emotions in front of are strong. There were no unique outliers discovered that might have influenced the

data distribution. Furthermore, because the data showed little difference in the scores of students who tested positive against those who did not test positive, bimodal data errors are unlikely. There were no concerns with multicollinearity, neighboring residuals, or auto-correlation, indicating that each variable was highly independent of one another and that no two variables measured the same constructs in part or whole.

A significant negative correlation between students tested negative and positive indicated that mitigations measures taken had no real impact on their social competence. Regression analysis of the two variables produced an R2 of -0.08% suggesting that -8% had a negative strong significance of less impact from mitigations measures taken to students' social competence. In situations when students tested positive, continued to use their social media and attend classes through the E-learning model. A strong negative individual correlation among variables suggests that Covid-19 mitigation measures and students' social competence have a negative strong relationship with one another. Moreover, there is little difference in social competence scores for students tested positive and negative, it suggest that both groups of students have no change in their social competence.

Conclusion.

Results revealed that Covid-19 mitigation measures have a little significant impact on students' social competence by looking at the range, scores remained between Good and a Very good level of social competence individual total scores. Our personality is incomplete without social skills. We utilize these abilities every day to communicate with friends and family. Students can communicate with each other more easily in a collaborative and interactive online learning environment. Students are introduced to different cognitive processes across cultures through small-group exercises using collaborative web technologies. They eventually acquire strong communication and social skills, which are essential for success in formal schooling at the next level (Desai, 2020). Several measures can be used to reduce the effects from pandemic on students' capability to communicate. Transparent masks, for example, can be used in terms of facilitating visual input in an in-person scenario. Facilitators should improve the visual and aural environment by deploying fit equipment, video chat features (such as chat, mute, and "raise hand" functionalities), and extra captioning, recording, and transcribing services. Accepting learners request to take a

break and get adequate rest in meetings will aid them to keep away being tired by online classes (Sara A. Charney, 2020).

The epidemic has affected people all across the world in many ways, including physical, psychological, and existential. The lack of awareness of pain among those who are not severely afflicted fails to sufficiently emphasize the difficulties linked with social interaction and competence, which go unaddressed. Around the world, educational institutions are aiming to provide pupils with techniques for dealing with positive social competence. Because students' usage of online classrooms and social media was discovered to be an emergency reaction, it might be supported as a viable coping strategy for maintaining good social competence abilities. In this study, the aim was to evaluate the changes in the social competence of students due to covid-19 mitigations measures for college students. In the current times of a pandemic crisis, it is important to help individuals fight in the field of social competence by improving personal adequacy, interpersonal adequacy, and communication skills. Awareness about the benefits of effective interpersonal situations and social roles for the general education system can be helpful for them and the whole community.

Previous studies on the impact of social competence from covid-19 mitigation measures taken in various countries on students. The challenges came from social and economic classes of students' families, the level of contamination among communities, the status of appropriate infrastructure for teaching, learning, and mental health issues. However, Bolatov and colleagues discovered that during the lockdown, when all teaching was conducted online, students were more satisfied with their academic achievement than before COVID-19, when traditional teaching techniques were used. They believe this explains the considerable and sustained drop in the prevalence of depressive symptoms reported over the COVID-19 period (The University of EDINBURGH, 2021). Similar studies can be also conducted in different social values settings that may be improving to the social competence of students in all educational perspectives. level with relation to their economical class of individuals like pupils' living conditions, extreme poverty, and environments where the internet and family financial means are critical to cope with the pandemic situation to predict proper solution if next same challenges happen.

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